

MEASURING THE IMPACT OF FACE-TO-FACE LEARNING ON HUMSS STUDENTS' SCHOOL PRODUCTIVITY

Arnel L. Villamor Jr. ¹, Lorraine Keith L. Cabig ¹, Nathalie Eryne O. Romero ¹,
Deeroy T. Guevarra ¹, Jake A. Pamintuan ¹, Jhaycel M. Santos ¹, Azumi Tadeo ¹,
Gian T. Aquino ¹, Joshua N. Montemayor ¹, John Louise M. Marcaida ²

¹ Senior High School Department, Our Lady of Fatima University, Philippines

² College of Arts and Sciences, Our Lady of Fatima University, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the impact of face-to-face learning on the productivity of Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences Strand students, concentrating on multifaceted aspects such as academic performance, completion of performance tasks, overall academic outcomes, student engagement, extra-curricular activities, and school attendance rates. Through a quantitative methodology employing random sampling (n=54) via an online survey, the study systematically investigates the productivity of Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences students. The researchers harnessed descriptive statistics for data analysis, unveiling a robust consensus among the participants. The respondents overwhelmingly expressed a positive outlook on the impact of face-to-face learning, with weighted means ranging from 3.43 to 3.49 and an overarching weighted mean of 3.45, indicative of a unanimous 'strongly agree' sentiment. These findings underscore the affirmative influence of physical classroom presence on various dimensions of student experience. The study asserts that the tangible presence in a classroom setting significantly contributes to the academic success, heightened engagement, and overall productivity of Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences Strand students. The research advocates for the sustained relevance of face-to-face learning, emphasizing its enduring importance within the educational landscape, thereby supporting the holistic development of students in this academic context.

Keywords: *face-to-face learning, student productivity, academic performance, school attendance rates, senior high school*

INTRODUCTION

For generations, traditional education has utilized face-to-face classes, a method in which teachers and students convene in a shared physical environment to learn together. This approach gained renewed attention during the pandemic when the global educational landscape was disrupted. Opinions about face-to-face classes vary widely, with some staunch advocates and others voicing concerns, fueling a spirited debate on the subject. In the past few years, the rise of technological innovations has resulted in an increasing dependence on digital platforms for educational use. This trend has reached its peak with the widespread acceptance of online or remote learning, driven by its convenience and accessibility. In light of this transition, it is essential to evaluate the lasting significance of face-to-face learning and its capacity to augment students' effectiveness in the educational environment.

As McQuaid (2022) indicated, a significant 97.5% of public schools have reinstated traditional five-day, in-person classes, leading to a noticeable improvement in educational approaches. Based on this information, it is evident that face-to-face learning remains the most trusted teaching method. Face-to-face education has a profound impact on the intricate dynamic between students and teachers. In-person learning offers students the chance to establish a more intimate and emotionally connected relationship with their teachers, a crucial aspect emphasized by Moè et al. (2022). In traditional classrooms, students have the opportunity to build stronger emotional ties with their teachers, a fundamental element. This connection forms the basis for trust and increased engagement, positively influencing both student behavior and academic performance. Furthermore, the research by Vago and Carvalhais (2022) emphasized the broader impact, suggesting that a positive student-teacher relationship creates an environment conducive to both academic and social development. In summary, these findings collectively emphasize the irreplaceable role of face-to-face learning in fostering the essential components of trust, engagement, and positive environments within the educational realm.

In-person instruction, commonly associated with traditional classrooms, provides a dynamic learning setting marked by direct interactions between teachers and students. This setting encourages lively discussions, practical activities, and immediate feedback, all recognized in prior research as essential components of effective learning. Active engagement between teachers and students significantly encourages student involvement, a critical aspect of classroom participation. Furthermore, the same study suggests that this interaction plays a vital role in cultivating a sense of accomplishment and self-efficacy among students, thereby enhancing their motivation to learn. Additionally, according to Zhan et al. (2021), these interactions have the potential to bolster student leadership skills, ultimately contributing to an enriched learning atmosphere.

In Stoian et al.'s study (2022), it is acknowledged that online education holds the potential to provide flexibility, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness. Nevertheless, face-to-

face education is highlighted for its capacity to offer social interaction, hands-on experience, and networking opportunities (p. 12812). Kemp and Grieve's research (2014) suggest that both online and face-to-face activities can result in similar academic performance levels, yet students express a preference for face-to-face activities. These findings may guide future researchers in delving deeper into the specific elements of face-to-face education that contribute to students' overall productivity. Such exploration could involve an examination of how social interaction and hands-on experiences impact the learning environment and influence student outcomes. In the ever-evolving educational landscape, the efficacy and relevance of traditional in-person instruction are being reexamined due to continual technological advancements. In this research endeavor, the researcher's objective is to thoroughly examine the impact of face-to-face learning on students' overall academic performance, engagement, and participation in extracurricular activities, as well as their school attendance rates.

Unveiling the Impact: Exploring Factors That Influence Academic Performance

One key theme in this study is the impact of face-to-face learning on students' academic performance. Researchers aim to understand how traditional classroom settings affect students' grades and their ability to complete performance tasks. Brew (2021) emphasized that educational success is gauged through students' academic accomplishments, reflecting their achievement levels and capacity for independent learning. It signifies their readiness to take responsibility for their educational journey, pursue dynamic career paths, and acquire knowledge and skills essential for a prosperous life. A range of factors, including environmental, social, economic, psychological, and educational elements, influence students' academic performance. While these factors exert a significant impact on academic outcomes, their manifestation varies across countries and among individuals. Previous studies predominantly focused on aspects such as gender, classroom environment, teacher training, instructional variations, family educational background, and socioeconomic contexts when investigating students' academic achievements.

In consideration to Högberg's (2023) research, the prevailing view is that achieving higher academic performance is generally advantageous, with the majority of quantitative studies indicating a weak positive correlation between performance and mental health. This research offers valuable insights into student performance outcomes, shedding light on the impact of face-to-face learning on academic achievements. Investigating the various elements that contribute to academic performance can establish a fundamental comprehension of the complex factors influencing students' achievements. When these insights are applied to the specific context of in-person learning, researchers can analyze how traditional classroom environments affect aspects like socio-economic status, study habits, and parental involvement. This enables a comprehensive understanding of the impact of face-to-face learning on students' school productivity. The findings from this study can serve as a roadmap for improving educational methods, shaping policies, and questioning or validating assumptions. In essence, this research contributes to a more nuanced comprehension of the correlation between face-to-face learning and academic success.

Student Engagement and Active Participation: Exploring Influences on Educational Success

Researchers are investigating whether in-person learning is associated with higher participation in school-related pursuits. According to Burton et al. (2018), engaging in various extracurricular activities can positively impact students' educational interest and learning outcomes. This implies that the physical presence of students in school for face-to-face learning may increase the likelihood of their involvement in extracurricular activities, thereby enhancing their overall educational experience. In a recent investigation, Hopkins et al. (2021) delved into the realm of out-of-classroom engagement encounters specifically tailored for first-generation college students. This exploration encompassed involvement in work, residence, athletics, clubs, organizations, and volunteer work. The primary objective of their research was to discern the effects of these engagement experiences on the persistence of students. The findings of this study highlight the crucial role that participation in diverse extracurricular activities plays in shaping the educational trajectories of students.

Based on these discoveries, one can reasonably propose that in-person education might result in higher levels of student involvement and active participation in school-related endeavors, including extracurricular activities. The immersive experiences and interpersonal interactions within traditional educational settings have the potential to inspire students to engage more actively in their academic community. Examining student engagement and active participation is essential for understanding the influence of in-person learning on students' academic performance. Evaluating the extent of engagement and participation allows researchers to measure the success of conventional classroom setups in nurturing an optimal learning atmosphere. Elevated levels of student engagement are frequently linked to heightened motivation, curiosity, and focus, all of which play a role in improving overall productivity. Ultimately, the establishment of a supportive, motivating, and efficient learning environment that fosters student success necessitates a thorough comprehension of the elements influencing student engagement and active involvement.

Analyzing School Attendance Rates and Their Impact on Academic Learning

The study examines how face-to-face learning impacts students' school attendance rates. This theme addresses whether being physically present in school encourages better attendance. In the study conducted by Sekiwu et al. (2020), it was noted that, although the variable of school attendance had minimal impact on academic performance, it did establish a significant positive correlation between attending school and achieving academic success. On a related note, Chisadza et al. (2021) underscore the significance of improving digital infrastructure and making internet access more affordable, especially in light of the challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic. According to their findings, these measures play a crucial role in mitigating the adverse effects on educational outcomes, underscoring the importance of promoting physical attendance at school, which is closely associated with increased attendance.

Furthermore, a positive correlation between students' participation in in-person classes and their involvement in virtual learning within a blended educational setting. Their findings suggest that students stand to gain advantages from a blend of conventional classroom participation and the inclusion of virtual learning elements. This suggests that being present in a physical classroom setting supports increased attendance rates, particularly when complemented by virtual learning options. Examining school attendance rates is essential for understanding how in-person learning impacts students' academic performance. Through data collection, educators and researchers can discover correlations between regular classroom attendance and students' success. A high attendance rate may indicate an active and engaged student body, suggesting a positive link between face-to-face learning and academic productivity. On the other hand, lower attendance rates may signify challenges or disinterest, prompting a closer evaluation of the effectiveness of in-person instruction. Uncovering the relationship between attendance and productivity offers valuable insights for improving educational approaches, underscoring the significance of face-to-face interactions in creating an optimal learning environment, and implementing interventions to boost overall academic achievement.

Research Questions

This study aims to measure the impact of face-to-face learning on students' productivity in school. The study specifically aims to give answers to the following questions:

1. What is the effect of face-to-face learning in students' grades?
2. What impact does face-to-face learning have on students' ability to complete performance tasks?
3. How does physical presence in a classroom setting influence overall academic outcomes?
4. What is the level of student engagement and participation in extracurricular activities in face-to-face learning?
5. What is the effect of face-to-face learning in students' school attendance rates?

METHODOLOGY

The research design that is employed in this study is a quantitative approach. According to Creswell (2014), Quantitative research involves the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data to describe characteristics, identify correlations, and test hypotheses. Employing random sampling is a strategic decision aimed at minimizing potential biases in the study outcomes. In ensuring a judicious representation of this population, the research opted for a systematic approach to respondent selection. The utilization of Taro Yamane's formula served as a methodological guide in determining the appropriate sample size. The participants were assembled using the Taro Yamane's

formula, which involves calculating the number of respondents using the equation $54 = 121 / (1 + 121 (0.10)^2)$.

In assessing the impact of face-to-face learning on students' school productivity, the researchers employed a research instrument in the form of a questionnaire consisting of 55 survey questions. The said instrument is divided into two parts which includes the demographic profile of the respondents and the specific questions to assess the study's objectives. A computer-generated software or specifically known as Google forms is used to disseminate and allocate the study's instrument. Upon completion of the data gathering process, the collected information is subjected to careful analysis, with a particular focus on testing the formulated hypotheses. The analysis contributes to uncovering insights into the potential positive effects of face-to-face learning on students' academic performance, engagement, and overall productivity. Throughout the entire process, confidentiality and privacy were prioritized, with informed consent obtained from participants at the outset, underscoring the commitment to safeguarding the sensitive information provided by the respondents. This commitment to confidentiality extends to the subsequent stages of analysis and reporting, reinforcing the ethical considerations in handling the gathered data. In analyzing the data, the researchers employed descriptive statistics to carefully summarize and analyze key aspects of our dataset. Descriptive statistics serve as concise informational coefficients that encapsulate a given dataset, serving as a representation of either an entire population or a sample. These statistics are categorized into measures of central tendency and measures of variability (spread).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age

Table 1 illustrates the demographic distribution based on age, outlining the frequency and percentage of respondents in each category. The data reveals that the majority of respondents, comprising 33 individuals (61.11%), fall within the 17 years old category, followed by 18 years old with 17 individuals (31.48%). The 16 years old group constitutes 2 individuals (3.70%), while both 19 years old and 23 years old groups each account for 1 individual (1.85%). This distribution provides an overview of the age composition of the surveyed individuals.

Sex

Also, Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on sex, detailing the frequency and percentage in each category. The data indicates an almost balanced representation of sex among the respondents, with the majority of females constituting 28 individuals (51.85%) and males comprising 26 individuals (48.15%) of the surveyed respondents. This breakdown provides insight into the sex composition of the study respondents.

Table 1**Descriptive Statistics of Respondent's Demographic Profile**

<i>Demographic Profile</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	16	2	3.70
	17	33	61.11
	18	17	31.48
	19	1	1.85
	23	1	1.85
Sex	Male	26	48.15
	Female	28	51.85

Effect on Students' Grades

In Table 2, the subscale focusing on the "Impact of Face-to-Face Learning on Students' Grades" reveals a weighted mean of 3.49 and a standard deviation of 0.58. The majority of respondents strongly agreed with this statement, as illustrated in the table. Previous studies have consistently highlighted lower academic performance in online courses when compared to traditional face-to-face classes. Despite these concerns, there remains uncertainty about online course performance, particularly given the notable attrition rates among enrolled students. Addressing such concerns, some research indicates that the incorporation of peer review assessments can boost final grades and positively influence students' overall perception of learning, as evidenced in study conducted by Mulder (2014).

Impact on Students' Proficiency in Completing Performance Tasks

Table 2 demonstrates a unanimous consensus that traditional face-to-face learning significantly contributes to students' proficiency in completing performance tasks, as evidenced by a weighted mean of 3.46, affirming strong agreement with a standard deviation of 0.54. Concurrently, a recent review by Nortvig et al. (2018) identified key factors influencing students' academic performance in both distance learning and blended learning environments. These factors encompassed the instructor's presence, interactive elements, content quality, and the integration of online and offline activities, including practice-oriented tasks. The three comprehensive review studies previously mentioned highlight the extensive body of literature comparing academic performance between face-to-face and distance learning. Additionally, various studies have delved into the impact of individual factors such as motivation, learning strategies, and cognitive abilities on academic outcomes, as demonstrated by Stark (2019). Similarly, research by El-Refae et al. (2019) has explored the distinctions and similarities in demographic characteristics, satisfaction levels, competencies, learning outcomes, and academic performance between face-to-face and distance learning modalities.

Impact of Physical Presence on Academic Achievement

As displayed in table 2, there is a strong agreement regarding the positive impact of physical presence on academic achievement. A weighted mean of 3.46 supports the idea that students perceive face-to-face learning as beneficial for academic success with standard deviation of 0.50. Angara et al. (2020) highlighted the significant potential impacts of the swift transition to the "New Normal" educational paradigm on learners' overall development. One notable concern is the potential effects of this new educational model and instructional delivery methods on students' mental health and emotional well-being. The use of emotions to enhance thinking and academic achievement is limited, but the understanding and regulation of emotions are strongly linked to scholastic success, particularly in terms of emotional understanding, which exhibits a robust correlation. Teachers who prioritize students' emotional intelligence tend to foster a friendly and conducive learning environment. An inherent characteristic of online learning is the temporal and spatial separation between teachers and learners. The flexibility provided by online courses, allowing independence from fixed schedules and physical locations, is a prominent feature that contributes to learners' convenience and adaptability.

Level of Student Engagement and Participation in Extracurricular Activities

As shown in table 2, the data indicates strong agreement that face-to-face learning contributes positively to student engagement and participation in extracurricular activities. The weighted mean of 3.43 suggests a generally favorable perception. The significance of extracurricular activities in a student's life is universally acknowledged. Aoyagi et al. (2020) conducted a study exploring the motivating factors behind students' engagement in various extracurricular activities. They identified key factors such as a sense of responsibility, continuity, the spirit of challenge, and advancement. Furthermore, Seow and Pan (2016) proposed a development framework that suggests a positive correlation between extracurricular activities and academic performance up to a certain threshold. However, they caution that excessive participation beyond this point may have detrimental effects on achievement. Specifically, they argue that if the time invested in extracurricular activities becomes so substantial that it displaces academically focused activities, it can hinder overall academic success.

Effect on Students' School Attendance Rates

The results on table 2 suggest strong agreement that face-to-face learning has a positive effect on students' school attendance rates. The weighted mean of 3.44 supports the notion that physical classroom presence positively influences attendance. Carminucci et al. (2021) reported similar findings, noting that students attending school in person tend to exhibit higher attendance rates in comparison to those primarily engaged in online instruction. Additionally, students generally express a preference for face-to-face learning over online modalities, citing increased engagement and the immediate feedback received during class discussions (Kemp & Grieve, 2014).

<i>Survey Questionnaires</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
<i>Effect of face-to-face learning in Students Grades</i>			
1. Do you think Grading Motivates Students to Learn?	3.51	0.54	Strongly Agree
2. Face-To-Face Helps you to Raise your Grades?	3.55	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. Can face-To-Face Help You to Facilitate the Lessons Easily?	3.64	0.48	Strongly Agree
4. Do your Grades Provide Reliable Information about Students grades?	3.33	0.61	Strongly Agree
5. Does the grading provide feedback to help you understand and improve your definitions?	3.42	0.68	Strongly Agree
6. After going back to traditional Face-To-Face Learning did it positively affect your Grades?	3.53	0.57	Strongly Agree
7. Face-to-Face Learning helps you to be more productive at school?	3.59	0.53	Strongly Agree
8. Doing your task at school fast and easy?	3.29	0.79	Strongly Agree
9. Face-to-face discussion helps you to understand the lesson more?	3.66	0.51	Strongly Agree
10. Does in person learning help your overall academics?	3.46	0.57	Strongly Agree
<i>Weighted mean</i>	3.49	0.58	Strongly Agree
<i>Impact of Face-to-Face Learning on Students' Proficiency in Completing Performance Tasks</i>			
1. In-person interactions with teachers or instructors have on student ability to complete performance tasks?	3.40	0.49	Strongly Agree
2. In your experience, do Face-to-face learning environments provide more immediate and effective feedback on your performance task?	3.30	0.52	Strongly Agree
3. When working on group performance tasks in a face-to-face setting, do you feel more accountable to your group members?	3.38	0.67	Strongly Agree
4. Does the physical presence of teachers or instructors in face-to-face learning impact your motivation to complete a performance task?	3.51	0.49	Strongly Agree
5. In Face-to-face learning, do you feel more engaged and actively involved when working on performance tasks?	3.38	0.52	Strongly Agree
6. Do you feel more accountable to your group when working on group performance tasks in face-to-face learning?	3.35	0.49	Strongly Agree
7. Do you receive more immediate and effective feedback on your performance task face-to-face learning?	3.35	0.50	Strongly Agree
8. Does face-to-face interaction with teachers and instructors help you better understand performance task requirements?	3.57	0.53	Strongly Agree
9. Does face-to-face learning have a positive impact on your ability to complete performance tasks?	3.51	0.51	Strongly Agree
10. Has face-to-face learning made it easier for you to demonstrate your skills in performance tasks?	3.46	0.65	Strongly Agree
<i>Weighted mean</i>	3.46	0.54	Strongly Agree
<i>Impact of physical presence on Academic Achievement.</i>			
1. To what extent do you believe that physical presence in a classroom positively impacts your ability to understand and grasp academic context.	3.42	0.49	Strongly Agree
2. Do you think face-to-face interactions with instructors during classroom sessions contribute significantly to your academic performance?	3.46	0.53	Strongly Agree
3. Does being physically present in a classroom enhance your focus and concentration during lectures?	3.46	0.65	Strongly Agree
4. To what extent do you believe that the physical classroom setting positively influences your ability to actively participate in class discussions?	3.50	0.50	Strongly Agree
5. Do you think having classmates physically present around you enhance your collaborative learning experiences?	3.42	0.53	Strongly Agree
6. Does the physical presence of classmates and instructors create a more engaging learning environment?	3.35	0.64	Strongly Agree
7. Do you find that physically attending classes helps in building a sense of community and belonging within the academic environment?	3.51	0.49	Strongly Agree
8. To what extent do you believe that face-to-face communication with instructors fosters a clearer understanding of course materials compared to online alternatives?	3.42	0.53	Strongly Agree
9. In your experience, does being present in the classroom positively impact your motivation to complete assignments and actively participate in coursework?	3.61	0.59	Strongly Agree

10. Do you feel that physical attendance in the classroom setting is essential for creating a more immersive and enriching learning experience?	3.46	0.49	Strongly Agree
Weighted mean	3.46	0.50	Strongly Agree
Level of student engagement and participation in extracurricular activities face-to-face.			
1. In your experience, do you believe that face-to-face learning positively influences students' active participation in extracurricular activities?	3.48	0.50	Strongly Agree
2. To what extent do you think the physical presence in a classroom setting encourages students to engage in extracurricular activities on campus?	3.42	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. Do you find that students who attend face-to-face classes are more likely to participate in clubs, sports, or other non-academic activities compared to those in online learning environments?	3.44	0.60	Strongly Agree
4. Does the traditional classroom setting contribute to a higher level of overall student engagement, including involvement in extracurriculars?	3.44	0.53	Strongly Agree
5. To what extent do you believe that face-to-face interactions with peers and instructors positively influence students' motivation to participate in extracurricular events?	3.37	0.52	Strongly Agree
6. Do you think students who attend classes in person are more likely to take on leadership roles in extracurricular activities compared to those in virtual learning environments?	3.37	0.70	Strongly Agree
7. Does the physical presence in a classroom foster a sense of community that encourages students to actively engage in extracurricular opportunities?	3.42	0.56	Strongly Agree
8. To what extent do you believe that students attending face-to-face classes have more opportunities for networking and forming connections that lead to involvement in extracurriculars?	3.44	0.53	Strongly Agree
9. Do you find that the traditional classroom environment positively impacts students' willingness to explore and participate in a variety of extracurricular activities?	3.48	0.50	Strongly Agree
10. In your opinion, does the level of student engagement in extracurricular activities increase with the presence of face-to-face learning compared to virtual or online learning environments?	3.48	0.60	Strongly Agree
Weighted mean	3.43	0.56	Strongly Agree
Effect of face-to-face learning in students' school attendance rates.			
1. Do you believe that face-to-face learning improves students' school attendance rates?	3.51	0.60	Strongly Agree
2. Having a choice between face-to-face and online learning affect school attendance rates?	3.44	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. Do you think that students feel more accountable and responsible when they attend face-to-face classes which may lead to better attendance rates?	3.57	0.56	Strongly Agree
4. Do you agree that face-to-face learning provides students with more opportunities to interact with other students and their teachers, which can positively impact their attendance rates?	3.57	0.49	Strongly Agree
5. To what extent do you believe that face-to-face interactions with teachers positively influence students' motivation to attend school on a regular basis?	3.50	0.49	Strongly Agree
6. Do you think students who attend classes in person are less likely to miss school days compared to those in virtual or online learning environments?	3.24	0.81	Strongly Agree
7. In your view, does the physical presence in a classroom contribute to a sense of responsibility and commitment among students regarding their attendance?	3.50	0.60	Strongly Agree
8. To what extent do you believe that students attending face-to-face classes have fewer instances of absenteeism compared to those in virtual or online learning environments?	3.31	0.68	Strongly Agree
9. Do you find that the traditional classroom environment positively influences students' sense of routine and discipline, leading to better school attendance?	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
10. Does the level of face-to-face interaction in the classroom have a direct impact on reducing truancy and improving overall school attendance rates?	3.44	0.53	Strongly Agree
Weighted mean	3.44	0.60	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.45	0.55	Strongly Agree

Conclusions

The following conclusions were derived from the pertinent results of this study.

1. The demographic profile of the respondents in this study encompasses their sex and age. The majority of respondents, comprising 33 individuals (61.11%), fall within the 17 years old category. The 18 years old group is represented by 17 individuals (31.48%). The 16 years old group constitutes 2 individuals (3.70%), while both the 19 years old and 23 years old groups each account for 1 individual (1.80%). There are 28 females (51.85%) and 26 males (48.15%) among the surveyed respondents.
2. The subscale "*Effect of face-to-face learning on Students Grades*" yielded a weighted mean of 3.49 with a standard deviation of 0.58, indicating a moderate to high level of agreement among the respondents. This suggests a positive perception among the surveyed individuals regarding the efficacy of face-to-face learning in influencing academic performance.
3. The subscale "*Impact of Face-to-Face Learning on Students' Proficiency in Completing Performance Tasks*" shows a strong agreement, with a weighted mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 0.54. This suggests a robust consensus among respondents that face-to-face learning positively influences students' performance task abilities.
4. The subscale "*Impact of Physical Presence on Academic Achievement*" demonstrates a strong agreement regarding the positive impact of physical presence on academic achievement, with a weighted mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 0.50. This indicates that students perceive face-to-face learning as beneficial for academic success, reinforcing a positive trend in their opinions.
5. The subscale "*Level of Student Engagement and Participation in Extracurricular Activities*" indicates strong agreement that face-to-face learning contributes positively to student engagement and participation in extracurricular activities. The weighted mean of 3.43 and a standard deviation of 0.56 suggests a generally favorable perception, highlighting the role of face-to-face learning in enhancing students' involvement beyond regular academic tasks.
6. The subscale "***Effect on Students' School Attendance Rates***" got the weighted mean of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 0.50 which supports the notion that physical classroom presence positively influences attendance. This further emphasizes the perceived importance of face-to-face instruction in promoting consistent attendance among students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were formulated based on the study's results.

1. Expand the demographic scope of the study by including a more diverse sample in terms of geographical location, socio-economic background, and cultural factors. This would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how various student populations perceive and benefit from face-to-face learning.
2. Conduct longitudinal studies to track the impact of face-to-face learning over an extended period. This approach can provide insights into the sustainability of positive perceptions and whether there are any evolving trends or changes in students' attitudes and productivity over time.
3. Explore comparative studies that analyze the impact of face-to-face learning in contrast to other learning modalities, such as fully online or hybrid approaches. This can offer a nuanced perspective on the effectiveness of different instructional methods and their influence on student productivity.
4. Complement quantitative findings with qualitative research methods, such as interviews or focus group discussions, to gain deeper insights into the subjective experiences and perceptions of students. Qualitative data can provide context and enrich the understanding of the factors influencing students' views on face-to-face learning.
5. Extend the research to include the perspectives of teachers and educational institutions. Investigate how educators perceive the impact of face-to-face learning on student productivity and explore any institutional strategies implemented to enhance the effectiveness of traditional classroom settings.
6. Given the increasing integration of technology in education, future research could delve into how technology affects the dynamics of face-to-face learning. Explore how the use of digital tools and resources in traditional classrooms influences students' engagement, performance, and overall productivity.
7. Consider the influence of cultural and contextual factors on students' perceptions of face-to-face learning. This could involve examining how cultural differences or specific contextual challenges may shape students' attitudes towards traditional classroom settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for

academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

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